

INTERACTIVE TOOLS OF TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH GRAMMAR FOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Annotation. This article is about the improvement of English grammar in the educational process using various methods. It discusses the teaching of English grammar to secondary school students in general secondary education, as well as provides a number of recommendations for the development of education.

Keyword. Grammatical theme, interactive methods, grammatical rules, tense, practice.

Introduction. Continuous education in Uzbekistan is aimed at forming the young generation with high professional culture, skills of independent adaptation to creative and social life, and the ability to define and solve future plans. It is important to be up- to-date in performing these tasks. Therefore, the role of foreign language, especially English, is very important in bringing up the young generation who know foreign languages well in the development of social, economic and scientific development of the society. The goals of English language teaching in the state educational standard and curriculum of general secondary education should be derived from the interests and requirements of the society and the state, and should be consistent with it. The developmental goal of teaching a foreign language includes the following: 1) the components of speech ability are listening, noticing, perception, distinguishing language phenomena, logical expression of thought, etc. 2) ability to communicate; emotion, approachability, eloquence, politeness, initiative during conversation, appropriate use of gestures, etc. 3) mental processes related to speech activity; thinking, memory attention, imagination, analysis and synthesis, generalization. 4) internal and external motivation, interest and enthusiasm for learning a foreign language and the country where the language is being studied, its people, culture, customs, etc. 5) independent work during education and preparation of students for independent education after completing education.

Based on the requirements of modern methodology, we chose an integrative approach to teaching grammatical phenomena. And some grammatical phenomena do not pose a great difficulty for mastering due to their similarity

with the grammatical phenomena of the mother tongue according to their meaning or construction methods. In the studies of linguist T. Sattorov, detailed information was given about this, and the idea of a stratified approach to grammatical phenomena was put forward. Information technologies in foreign language education recommended for wide use. Consequently, we found it necessary to use the following information technologies in the process of teaching students grammatical phenomena: computer technology, interactive methods, open discussion (dispute), excursion, auction, press conference, competition, dream intention, foreign language teaching project method, etc. When interactive methods are used, the student thinks independently and works as a partner with the teacher. Internet technologies are one of the most modern forms of information acquisition and communication in improving grammar skills of students in English classes. Students write lectures and abstracts using the internet.

The role of electronic dictionaries is incomparable for secondary school students to enhance vocabulary. In the electronic dictionary, words are pronounced directly as a set of sounds, not through a graphic representation. When working with such dictionaries, it is easy to remember words and they are stored in long-term memory. A test is taken to check and strengthen students' knowledge. During the test, students have the opportunity to work independently and self-asses. It is known that knowledge obtained independently is stored in the memory for a long time and is easy to recall. Strategy and game-tasks from modern technologies prevent students from getting bored and provide them with independent mental activity.

The task of the teacher is not to teach, but to facilitate the learning process. The lesson is oriented. Educational content; proximity to reality of students, students are encouraged to independently construct their knowledge. Advantages of the method: preparing students for real life, real life situations. Disadvantages of the method: at the present stage, they have not yet manifested themselves clearly enough. An example of a constructivist method is project-based learning. In education, attention is focused on the issue of teaching the student to think, to understand the opinion of others and to be able to express this opinion in oral and written form. The way of life and cultural creativity of the nations are studied on the basis of its rich historical heritage. Also, it becomes one of the close assistants of students in fulfilling the responsible task of choosing their direction and forming the skills of preparation for independent life. Below we give recommendations on the implementation of modern methods of teaching

based on certain topics in the class section. You can use it in a creative way, and our first President said that: " Let's look for an answer to the question: What are we doing today to instill in our children a sense of pride, and devotion to our motherland, which is sacred for every age?", we hope that you will contribute to achievement the intended goal by implementing modern methods of education and training.

In this article, as a result of the use of modern approaches and innovative methods in teaching English in secondary grades, the development of students' logical thinking skills, fluency in speech, the formation of the ability to quickly and correctly answer, instilling enthusiasm for knowledge, information is given about the effort to prepare thoroughly for classes.

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